

#SCI4NET0

INTERDISCIPLINARITY FOR THE NET-ZERO TRANSITION

The Perspectives of Universities and Research Organisations

REPORT OF 3 NOVEMBER 2022 COP27 LEAD-UP EVENT

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COLOPHON

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'Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition: the Perspectives of Universities and Research Organisations'

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KEY MESSAGES

CESAER, the [European University Association](#) (EUA), the [International Sustainable Campus Network](#) (ISCN), [Science Europe](#), the [Network of Universities from Capital Cities of Europe](#) (UNICA), and the [University of Strathclyde](#) (Glasgow, UK), jointly organised the COP27 lead-up event on 'Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition' on 3 November 2022. This Symposium came about following the [Call to Action](#) to Research and Higher Education Organisations for the Net-Zero Transition, launched at COP26 held in Glasgow in November 2021.

This report is based on the Symposium, which took stock of the progress made by universities and research organisations towards the Call to Action, welcoming new partners, and relaunching the commitments to climate actions. Universities and research organisations presented their strategies to engage with the Net-Zero Transition.

The following key messages were delivered at the Symposium:

1. The institutional leaders acknowledge and support the importance of interdisciplinarity in research and teaching to promote the Net-Zero Transition. Several interdisciplinary initiatives exist to effectively tackle the climate crisis, but they need to be scaled up to accelerate the Net-Zero Transition. Research stakeholders' organisations should provide visibility of good practices, facilitate knowledge exchange, and support at the organisational level.
2. Many universities, research funders and performers are already 'greening' their activities by reducing emissions. These efforts should be promoted as examples to inspire other sectors to accelerate their transition to Net-Zero, building trust among actors and motivating change.
3. Students are clearly recognised as a powerful force in engaging with the Net-Zero Transition. Their involvement in interdisciplinary teaching and research activities, and with research stakeholders' organisations, brings positive change and should be further encouraged. Students are the future leaders, professionals, and experts: by embracing the values of the UN Sustainable Development Goals, they can become the agents of change for climate sustainability.
4. Universities and research organisations should support policy development and implementation for the Net-Zero Transition at all levels, in a joint effort to tackle the climate crisis. Examples showing the support of local communities with researchers and students engaged with societal challenges has proven to be effective. The direct involvement of researchers and students, supported by their organisations, can have meaningful impact, even with limited funding. These interdisciplinary communities serve as foundation for developing research projects, teaching programmes and other initiatives that can effectively contribute to the Net-Zero Transition.
5. The establishment of common platforms with universities, research organisations, governments, business sectors, and other societal stakeholders should be encouraged to tackle the climate crisis. Research and higher education communities are considered among the most neutral stakeholders for tackling these societal challenges. They can play a crucial role in mobilising all actors. Stakeholders' engagement should take place at both international and local levels to accelerate the transition towards Net-Zero.

Finally, the Symposium co-organisers agreed to reconvene ahead of COP28 to develop their commitment further, involving new partners and proposing joint actions for systemic change towards the Net-Zero Transition.

BACKGROUND

Egypt hosted the twenty-seventh United Nations' Climate Change Conference of the Parties (COP27) in Sharm El-Sheikh from 6 to 18 November 2022. The annual climate conference brought more than 33,000 delegates from over 100 countries, represented by their Heads of State and governments. The focus for COP27 was on implementing climate actions, with a specific emphasis on how to finance them. A keyword from the final [declarations](#) shows the need to shift towards more concrete actions and implement the COP decisions. COP28 will take place in Dubai (United Arab Emirates) from 30 November to 12 December 2023.

The climate crisis calls for immediate, urgent actions to reduce emissions in all sectors and levels. At COP26 in Glasgow (UK) in 2021, [CESAER](#), the [International Sustainable Campus Network \(ISCN\)](#), [Science Europe](#), and the [University of Strathclyde](#) launched a [Call to Action](#) to Research and Higher Education Organisations for the Net-Zero Transition, based on the willingness to act together for climate actions. A [report of the 2021 edition](#) is available. The [European University Association \(EUA\)](#) and the [Network of Universities from Capital Cities of Europe \(UNICA\)](#) joined the collaboration in 2022 and co-organised the 2022 Symposium on 'Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition', as presented in this report.

The common aim is to enhance the contributions of research funders and performers, universities, and higher education institutions to tackle the climate crisis by reducing emissions and embodying the principles of climate sustainability. Following the spirit of the Call to Action, the six partners share *"a vision of a collaborative, systems-based approach, where research and education systems work together and in conjunction with industry and society at large, engaging in, and contributing to this crucial societal challenge"*. Six areas of intervention were identified in the 2021 Call to Action (in line with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal #13 '[Climate Action](#): take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts'):

1. Responding to the complexity of the Net-Zero challenges by addressing them in an interdisciplinary way.
2. Developing the next generation of students and researchers for the Net-Zero Transition.
3. Reducing our own organisational carbon footprint.
4. Supporting the Net-Zero Transition in policymaking at all levels.
5. Improving the shared understanding of what needs to be done.
6. Facing the challenges together.

The partners agreed to reconvene every year and engage with each other, as well as with new partners, such as EUA and UNICA in 2022. The six organisations agreed to take joint actions to tackle the climate crisis and chose the theme of 'interdisciplinarity' as the keyword to express the willingness to mobilise all actors, approaches, and stakeholders towards the Net-Zero Transition.

This report presents the key elements discussed at the Symposium 'Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition', held online on 3 November 2022 (see the Programme on page 14–15). It summarises the key elements of this challenge and actions that the research and university organisations are taking to tackle the climate crisis. Speakers were invited to bring their organisations' viewpoints, providing examples and experiences that could inspire other organisations to engage with the Net-Zero Transition. Integrating the different organisations' viewpoints aims to promote a systems-thinking approach, acknowledging the importance of all parts of the research and higher education communities. The overarching goal is to mobilise other stakeholders in joint efforts to tackle the climate crisis more effectively and rapidly.

ACTING TOGETHER FOR THE NET-ZERO TRANSITION

VIEWS FROM THE INSTITUTIONAL LEADERS

The climate crisis is a 'wicked' problem calling for mobilisation across all sectors, those engaged with research and higher education, and all our societies. The complexity of this challenge requires inter- and trans-disciplinary approaches to mobilise scientific approaches and stakeholders, assuming a systems-thinking perspective. These aspects for the discussion were introduced by [Lidia Borrell-Damián](#), Secretary General of Science Europe, who stated that *"interdisciplinarity is something that we believe is of utmost importance to tackle the challenges related to the Net-Zero Transition."* Her introduction emphasised the importance of identifying and then scaling up the most relevant initiatives to speed up the transition towards climate-sustainable research and higher education sectors. Since 2021, CESAER, ISCN, Science Europe, and the University of Strathclyde have started working together, and in 2022 they welcomed EUA and UNICA in this joint effort.

The session featuring institutional leadership was moderated by [Tim Bedford](#), Associate Principal for Research and Innovation at the University of Strathclyde (Glasgow, UK). He presented the 2021 Call to Action to research and higher education organisations for the Net-Zero Transition, launched in 2021 by CESAER, ISCN, Science Europe, and the University of Strathclyde. The 2022 edition welcomes EUA and UNICA as co-organisers of the Symposium, as they expressed their interest in acting together with the other partners towards the Net-Zero Transition.

The institutional leaders supported the key message that **all disciplines and stakeholders should be mobilised for the Net-Zero Transition**. Climate actions are needed from all research and teaching communities with more integrated, i.e. interdisciplinary, approaches. They reported several initiatives, as presented below, inviting others to join efforts, disseminating success stories, and promoting co-ordinated actions and initiatives. Two fundamental goals were identified: reducing the emissions within their organisations (i.e. universities, research funders and performers) and advocating more policy support in the transition towards climate-sustainable societies. These engagements should act as an example for research stakeholders' organisations and their members across Europe and beyond.

[Rik Van de Walle](#), President of CESAER and Rector at Gent University (Belgium), stated the importance of linking science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) with social science and humanities (SSH) to address the climate crisis. Working with colleagues from different areas/backgrounds helps to better direct research and teaching activities towards acting sustainably and embodying the principles of sustainability. He underlined that universities must continue to educate and train students and learners to (i) be aware of the challenges and their responsibilities, (ii) grow through problem- and challenge-based learning and teaching by being aware of their impacts on climate; and (iii) to act and live sustainably. He raised the open challenge of 'teaching university teachers' and how to do this effectively.

The role of **research stakeholders' organisations**, as they represent, should be to **identify and promote best practices**. Even small-scale projects can be effective; giving them visibility will inspire others to engage with the Net-Zero Transition. In the Call to Action, the partners commit to 'lead by example' towards reducing climate-harmful emissions. As several experiences are being developed, research stakeholders' organisations should encourage their members to promote, fund, and support concrete actions for the Net-Zero Transition.

The Vice-President of Science Europe, [Angelika Kalt](#) (Director of the Swiss National Science Foundation, SNSF), announced the publication of a new report by Science Europe on '[Interdisciplinary](#)

[Research for the Net-Zero Transition](#)'. This survey-based report presents the multiplicity of actions taken by Science Europe Member Organisations to fund and perform interdisciplinary research activities, providing recommendations on how to support the transition towards climate-sustainable research. While there is evidence of the effectiveness of these experiences, she invited to **scale up** these initiatives, focusing on concrete actions and pragmatic approaches. She relaunched the importance of acting together, universities with research funding and performing organisations, for a systems-thinking approach, able to mobilise all disciplines and stakeholders.

Promoting concrete actions aims to build trust and reinforce the credibility of the research and higher education communities vis-à-vis policy makers and the broader society. As the climate crisis requires collective, co-ordinated efforts, all actors should be involved. [Michael Murphy](#), President of the European University Association (EUA), presented the case of the University College Cork (UCC) in Ireland, where he was previously President. UCC was among the first universities in the world to get the Green Flag from the International Foundation for Environmental Education. This award was possible because UCC put the students in charge of co-ordinating the activities on campus. Thanks to the students, the initiative grew, involving secondary schools in the neighbourhoods, and then it spread across the whole of Ireland. Similar initiatives are emerging across all European universities, supporting the transition towards Net-Zero.

Students are acknowledged as **a positive force for change** also by [Luciano Saso](#), President of UNICA and Vice-Rector for European University Networks at the Sapienza University of Rome (Italy). He explained that students were the leading force asking for more sustainable-oriented initiatives. UNICA answered this demand by creating a specific axis of activities for sustainability, especially at the local/city level. This angle is especially relevant, given that UNICA member universities are located in capital cities and have a particular impact on the policy makers in their countries. The scope of these activities was progressively expanded to include all the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). Finally, he announced that UNICA have formally subscribed to the Call to Action to further reinforce their commitment and join the collective effort with the other organisations.

Tackling the climate crisis requires co-ordination among organisations aligning their strategies to maximise results across different policy fields and contexts, facilitating the growth of the most relevant initiatives. In this respect, [the agreement on the reforming of research assessment](#), elaborated under the responsibility of the EU Commission with EUA and Science Europe playing a pivotal role, and [DORA](#) are examples of multiple stakeholders' engagement in a cultural change for a better research system. The transition towards Net-Zero should follow a similar path with the engagement of all the actors in pursuit of a common goal. In this perspective, a negative signal comes from the European Green Deal that the European Commission launched in 2020 without any reference to the role of universities as enablers for the green transition. Nonetheless, the EUA has engaged with policy makers to improve this situation (see the [EUA vision on the European Green Deal](#)).

A new mindset is required, and initiatives such as the [Global University Associations Forum](#), launched in June 2022 by the EUA and eight homologue associations worldwide, contribute to the exchange of information and create a space for collective advocacy opportunities. As an example of advocacy, CESAER and UNICA published a [joint open letter](#) on effective funding for inter- and trans-disciplinary research. This letter invited European and national research funding organisations to provide more funding instruments, especially for early-career researchers. The objective of this is to build the capacity for larger collaborative and high-risk research projects, which are more likely to contribute to the Net-Zero Transition. A relevant element of the open letter is the need to move from 'single principal investigator' to 'co-principal investigator' and 'leading team of (early-career) researchers'. For instance, when applying for a project, researchers must indicate a specific faculty, de facto binding the application into a single discipline. The reform of

how research is assessed and thus rewarded is indeed flawed, and radical change still needs to be seen at the institutional level.

The ISCN President [Gisou van der Goot](#), Vice-President for Responsible Transformation at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne (EPFL), stated that universities have an image of neutrality and a fact-based approach, which hold added values to overcome political divisions and mobilise all parts of societies acting together for the Net-Zero Transition. Universities can **link the local and global scales** addressing the climate crisis, articulating this challenge across disciplines, and interacting with other actors. The ISCN is especially engaged with its new Latin American Chapter, which is proving to be highly valuable, particularly for providing mutual learning across continents. Universities have a contract with society, from which trust is fundamental: universities are called to pursue practical actions, from reducing their carbon footprint to changing the incentives and rewards for research activities to enhance the transition towards Net-Zero. This change is only possible if all actors work towards the same direction, ensuring students' involvement in this much-needed directional shift.

Other opportunities to accelerate the Net-Zero Transition come from the [European University Alliances](#), in which many CESAER, EUA, ISCN, and UNICA members are involved. These alliances provide the opportunity to give more visibility to climate actions, share good practices and improve the transition towards Net-Zero. More than 40 Alliances were established with the possibility of developing joint actions with financial and organisational support. These alliances also provide the opportunity to discuss and tackle problems in a co-ordinated manner, such as legal constraints and organisational differences that delay and frustrate efforts to move to a Net-Zero Transition.

Finally, the institutional leadership invited all actors to put more effort into tackling the climate crisis. The slower pace of the Net-Zero Transition should not discourage the research and higher education communities. On the contrary, it is a common objective that should motivate all actors. The mobilisation of all disciplines, including social science and humanities, facilitates the replicability of technical solutions across different socio-cultural contexts.

INTERDISCIPLINARY ACTIONS FOR THE NET-ZERO TRANSITION

THE VIEWS OF RESEARCH FUNDERS AND UNIVERSITIES

The first of the two experts' panels discussed the cases of interdisciplinary actions for the Net-Zero Transition in the case of research funding organisations and universities. A definition of interdisciplinarity was proposed by the moderator [Douglas Halliday](#) (Durham University, UK), a member of the EUA Green Deal task-and-finish group: interdisciplinarity is when *"experts and researchers from different backgrounds and expertise work together on a specific challenge."* This definition implies the willingness to co-operate respecting the different disciplinary viewpoints, as they are all valuable in addressing societal challenges. Interdisciplinarity requires new communication methods, going beyond a single discipline's vocabulary. These efforts would broaden the perspective and consider multiple factors, revealing the complexities that were sometimes previously hidden.

The experts from the first panel identified the success factor for interdisciplinary co-operation in **communities** gathered to tackle societal challenges, such as the Net-Zero Transition. The climate crisis is a *"now or never"* situation, as stated by [Melissa Brown Goodall](#) (ISCN member and Director of the Environmental Innovations Initiative at the University of Pennsylvania, USA). Universities are among the world's oldest institutions and are called to play their role in the Net-Zero Transition. A *"stubborn optimist"*, she invited everyone to *"cast a positive vision for the future and get people working toward it, [because] that's going to be a much more effective tool."*

In this perspective, she presented the case of Pennsylvania University, which called on all disciplines to explain how they address the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Researchers were invited to express their understanding of and **build commitment to societal challenges**. This approach also benefits students, as they are motivated to engage with societal challenges during their programmes. The university funds research communities not as projects but as local initiatives for researchers meeting monthly to engage with societal challenges. These communities have proven helpful for the emergence of new projects and initiatives. The success factor relies on the micro-level with direct contacts among researchers getting personally involved in SDG-oriented challenges.

A similar experience was presented by the Polytechnic University of Madrid (UPM) in Spain. [Alberto Garrido](#), UPM Vice-Rector for Quality and Efficiency and Secretary of the CESAER Task Force Sustainability, explained that UPM asks its professors how their courses relate to the SDGs. Despite being based on self-declaration, this approach has proven beneficial in making academic professors think and thus engage with societal challenges in their teaching. Furthermore, UPM created thematic research communities around SDG-related topics, two of which are for 'decarbonisation' and 'emissions-free university'. These UPM communities have dedicated managers to promote collaboration, share research infrastructure and develop new teaching programmes. These thematic communities effectively broaden the technological and scientific perspectives around societal challenges. This initiative provided evident win-win collaborations, especially by investing resources at the start-up phase: *"we need to invest resources, put some effort, some support, and let them go"*, as he effectively summarised.

The perspective of research funding organisations was presented by [Malin Mobjörk](#), Senior Research Officer at Formas and Chair of the Science Europe Working Group on the Green and Digital Transition. The challenge of interdisciplinary research is linked with researchers' career paths and evaluation approaches: research funding organisations like Formas encourage interdisciplinarity, but this effort should be supported over the longer term, beyond funding

single interdisciplinary projects. **Interdisciplinarity should be embedded in research careers**, rewarding these activities, especially among early-career researchers. She co-authored Science Europe's report '[Interdisciplinary Research for the Green and Digital Transition](#)', mapping the existing experiences across Science Europe Member Organisations. The first lesson learnt is that interdisciplinary research is defined in a very open sense and is related to how disciplines are conceptualised across countries, organisations, and contexts. As disciplines constantly evolve, different labels exist around the fundamental idea of mobilising multiple scientific approaches for a common goal. This multi-actor approach should also involve non-academic stakeholders, such as industry, government, NGO, and citizens. Interdisciplinarity is needed for 'wicked' problems, of which climate change and the Net-Zero Transition are clear examples.

The importance of interdisciplinary communities was also evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, as explained by the Co-ordinator of the UNICA Green and SDGs Working Group, [Matthew Lawson](#) (University of Edinburgh, UK). The COVID-19 crisis demonstrated that, by adopting instrumental and interdisciplinary approaches, universities could **break down silos**, support innovation and encourage collaboration with industry and society at large. This interdisciplinary approach should be strengthened and implemented by universities for the Net-Zero Transition to ensure that students and early-career researchers critically engage and experience the value of interdisciplinarity in learning, teaching, and research. This shift is essential for preparing students to be future leaders: Edinburgh University has developed new structures to support interdisciplinary research, such as the [Edinburgh Earth Initiative](#) and the [Futures Institute](#). These interdisciplinary initiatives aim to change university cultures, embedding the value of collaboration across disciplines.

The experts agreed that this change towards interdisciplinary co-operation benefits all university and research communities, including staff and alumni. Suitable **structures and resources** should be in place to **facilitate co-ordination**, which requires better communication among units and departments. Adopting interdisciplinary approaches is responding to students' demand for more sustainable universities and brings about positive change directly in teaching activities and for the future career of students.

The sense of community and **identity** are the factors to be encouraged, involving researchers and students across disciplines. Hiring staff with multiple affiliations, providing seed funding for challenge-driven research communities, and involving students to engage with the climate crisis were presented as examples of actions to support these communities. These interdisciplinary and multi-actor initiatives boost the motivation of those involved. This pro-active engagement is rewarded when problems arise because the actors involved are keener looking for constructive solutions. However, the success of these initiatives depends on the support given to them by their organisations.

INTERDISCIPLINARY ACTIONS FOR THE NET-ZERO TRANSITION

THE POLICY AND INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVES

The second experts' panel on the policy and international perspectives focused on the importance of interdisciplinarity to engage with stakeholders towards the Net-Zero Transition. The moderator [Peter Kaderjak](#), Head of the Zero Carbon Hub (ZKK) of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) in Hungary, started by highlighting the added value of interdisciplinarity to provide solutions at the local and global levels. The Net-Zero Transition requires new, urgent action to speed up the required change, and radical change is needed at all levels. He opened the discussion by asking if the research communities are ready for this change?

Changes must be radical because the incremental ones are no longer sufficient, as stated by [Sam Barratt](#), Chief of the Youth, Education and Advocacy unit of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). The Net-Zero Transition requires transformative actions for systemic change. Universities can play a crucial role because, by educating about 250 million students worldwide every year, they have the responsibility and incredible opportunity to shift young people's behaviours and norms. He invited universities to take more radical approaches being less conservative and more ambitious in their work.

Several examples of multi-stakeholder engagement were presented and discussed. At the UN level, wildfires are a harrowing example, with climate change making this challenge even more urgent. As the UN has limited staff to work on this highly complex challenge, they set up a panel of academic experts to identify actions to mitigate the risks posed by wildfires by planting differently and concentrating the limited available budget on crucial factors to reduce the risk. This example shows **the importance of mobilising university experts** to tackle a societal challenge.

[Luis Alberto Serra-Barragán](#) (Associate Dean of Research and Executive Director of the Energy Initiative at Tecnológico de Monterrey in Mexico) presented the 'multilevel' initiative of the university plan to reduce emissions and how this was the base to engage with municipalities sharing the same objective. Many local communities in Mexico see evident damages from climate change, and this mobilises everybody. Internally, Tec Monterrey engaged researchers from different disciplines to develop and implement plans to reduce emissions. These experiences grew and became the base for collaborations with the federal government of Mexico and then with the governments of Costa Rica and Chile to develop decarbonisation and water management strategies. The case of Tec Monterrey has become exemplary for its interdisciplinary approach and **capacity to scale up its activities** in tackling climate change. A tangential benefit of this experience is the opportunity to train new interdisciplinary researchers and create specialised units to interact with industries and governments, building organisational capacities over time.

Another example of stakeholders' engagement comes from the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). Since 2018, CSIC has established more than 30 [interdisciplinary thematic platforms](#) around societal challenges, as presented by [Pablo del Río](#), CSIC researcher and member of the Science Europe Working Group for the Green and Digital Transition. This mission-based platform gathered more than 600 research groups from CSIC involving industries, policy makers and other societal stakeholders. Furthermore, CSIC published a series of [white books](#) identifying and discussing society-relevant challenges from an interdisciplinary perspective. These examples successfully overcame the difficulties of gathering different disciplinary groups, developing a shared understanding and removing siloes in favour of more interactive processes.

Climate change has substantial **health implications**, as presented by [Matt Dolf](#) (University of British Columbia, Canada), Co-Chair of the International Health Promoting Universities and Colleges Network. Interdisciplinarity is needed to be able to also consider these health-related issues for the Net-Zero Transition. The [Okanagan Charter](#), an International Charter for Health Promoting Universities and Colleges, has proven to be an effective framework in mobilising university communities to tackle health issues related to climate change. For instance, the UBC campus was used as a living lab where faculty members, staff and students were called to develop ideas to reduce emissions for the whole community. This initiative seeded key projects and led to becoming a university-wide strategy to reduce emissions. This example was mentioned to inspire other universities to raise their ambitions.

Stakeholders' engagement requires **institutional support**, i.e. funding, recognition, and adequate rewards. A fundamental change in how research is assessed is needed, especially for early-career researchers who engage with the Net-Zero Transition. Research organisations should recognise that they are not isolated, but are expected to work with partners to address these challenges. Interdisciplinarity requires having the right incentives, both from the top down and from the bottom up.

Finally, the panel agreed that interdisciplinarity starts by **changing the university's organisational architecture and researchers' career paths**. Multidisciplinary communities should be cultivated around societal challenges, although it might be difficult to quantify the benefits and returns might be delayed. Despite all these challenges, opting for interdisciplinary approaches is rewarding, especially for young researchers and students who express their interest in engaging with the Net-Zero Transition.

CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This event was a tangible sign of the willingness to work together towards the Net-Zero Transition. Every speaker represented their organisation showing the activities already underway and the importance of mobilising all disciplines and involving industry, policy makers, and the broader society in this existential challenge. The Net-Zero Transition is happening, but all research and higher education community members are invited to accelerate their efforts and mobilise to scale up these initiatives. Research stakeholders' organisations, as those co-organising the Symposium, can gather these experiences, giving visibility and support. Promoting and supporting best practices can accelerate the Net-Zero Transition across universities and research organisations.

The leaders of the institutes that organised the symposium highlighted the value of interdisciplinary co-operation for the Net-Zero Transition, and in general, against climate change. Their commitment to tackle the climate crisis will continue, following the engagement expressed in the Call to Action launched in 2021. They relaunched the invitation to other research and higher education organisations to work together, adopting a systems-thinking perspective and, involving more stakeholders for the much-needed systemic change.

PROGRAMME

Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero Transition

THURSDAY 3 NOVEMBER 2022

14.00–14.05 CET

OPENING AND WELCOME

- Lidia **BORRELL-DAMIÁN**, Secretary General of Science Europe

14.05–14.50

First Panel

INTERDISCIPLINARY ACTIONS FOR THE NET-ZERO TRANSITION: THE VIEWS OF RESEARCH FUNDERS AND UNIVERSITIES

Moderator

- Douglas **HALLIDAY**, Durham University & EUA Green Deal task-and-finish group

Speakers

- Melissa **BROWN GOODALL**, Senior Director of the Environmental Innovations Initiative at the University of Pennsylvania and member of the International Sustainable Campus Network, ISCN
- Alberto **GARRIDO**, Vice-Rector for Quality and Efficiency at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid & Secretary of CESAER Task Force Sustainability
- Matthew **LAWSON**, University of Edinburgh & Co-ordinator of the UNICA Green and SDGs working group
- Malin **MOBJÖRK**, Senior Research Officer at Formas & Chair of the Science Europe's working group on the Green and Digital Transition

14.50–15.00

Break

15.00–15.45

Second Panel

INTERDISCIPLINARY ACTIONS FOR THE NET-ZERO TRANSITION: THE POLICY AND INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVES

Moderator

- Peter **KADERJAK**, Head of Zero Carbon Hub (ZKK), Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)

Speakers

- Sam **BARRATT**, Chief of Youth, Education and Advocacy of United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)
- Pablo **DEL RÍO**, Researcher at CSIC (Spain) and member of Science Europe Working Group for the Green and Digital Transition
- Matt **DOLF**, Co-Chair of the International Health Promoting Universities and Colleges Network & University of British Columbia
- Luis Alberto **SERRA-BARRAGÁN**, Associate Dean of Research and Executive Director of the Energy Initiative at Tecnológico de Monterrey

15.45–16.00

Break

16.00–17.00

Third Panel

ACTING TOGETHER FOR THE NET-ZERO TRANSITION

Opening Remarks & Moderator

- **Tim BEDFORD**, Associate Principal for Research and Innovation at University of Strathclyde
- **Rapporteurs from First and Second Panels**

Speakers

- **Angelika KALT**, Vice-President of Science Europe
 - **Michael MURPHY**, President of EUA
 - **Luciano SASO**, President of UNICA
 - **Gisou VAN DER GOOT**, President of International Sustainable Campus Network
 - **Rik VAN DE WALLE**, President of CESAER
-

17.00–17.05

CONCLUDING REMARKS AND NEXT STEPS

- **Lidia BORRELL-DAMIÁN**, Secretary General of Science Europe

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